

**A Correlation between Divorce, Separation and Academic Success of
Secondary School Students in Akwa Ibom
South Senatorial District, Nigeria**

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Abstract

This study determined the correlation between divorce, separation and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District, Nigeria. Two research questions were raised and two hypotheses formulated and tested at .05 level of significance. A correlational research design was adopted while the study population comprised all the 15,222 senior secondary two (SS2) students in the 63 public secondary schools in the area of study. A sample size of 375 SS2 selected for the study using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination table. A random sampling was used to sample 25 public secondary schools out of 63. Thereafter, the same random sampling method was used to select 15 students from each of the sampled schools for instrument administration which gave a total of 375 sampled respondents. The researcher's designed instrument titled "Divorce, Separation and Academic Success of Students Questionnaire (DSASSQ) were used for data collection, with overall reliability co-efficient of 0.76 for the independent variables and 0.88 for items measuring students' academic success, using Cronbach Alpha statistics. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics was used for data analysis and the study finding revealed a low negative and insignificant relationship between divorce, separation and academic success of secondary school students'. The researchers recommended among other things that, religious leaders and marriage counsellors should enlighten parents on the need to stay together as husband and wife in order to avoid effects of divorce on their student's academic work.

Keywords: Divorce, Separation, Academic Success, Marriage, Married Couples.

Introduction

Marriage is the legalizing of a special relationship between a man and woman to which the society gives approval, placed under legal and social obligations. In the process of maintaining social interaction and relationship, the family intimately held together by a bond of social and kinship relationship may experience challenges due to variation in family background, values and demands. According to Lesmin and Sarker (2018), marital conflict is the major cause of marital instability in the society. The author defined marital conflict as a situation in which there are disagreement and unpleasant feelings between the husband and wife, which can result in separation

and divorce. Marital conflict can occur if the spouses do not spend sufficient time together or if they do not have common interests.

Marriage between a man and woman is expected to be a permanent affair and lasting association until death takes away one of the partners; but due to changes in people's behaviour, attitude, belief and perception, some people see marriage as a temporary affair which can be dissolved either by cruelty, separation, divorce among others. Odey (2020) reported that the then wife of Akwa Ibom State Governor, Mrs. Martha Emmanuel decried the high rate of divorce and separation among couples in the state, with over 2,500 cases filed in Uyo High Court. This is outrageous and such condition if not addressed may threaten the household stability as well as the well-being of the children, as it often impacts on their academic success. The family stability often has a marked influence on the students' motivation for learning and on her to cope with academics. The home environment is a strong pointer to the academic success of children. This is because a number of children's academic potentials are now confronted with increasing difficulties as a result of parental marital disharmony.

The contact between the parent, teachers and students makes a lot of impact on the academic success of the students. Castro-Martin and Bumpass (2019), those who do not regularly attend classes because of lack of proper care, monitoring and supervision by the parents could experience challenges of performing better academically. In order for students to succeed academically, the closeness and support between the parents and children is very essential. According to Nseabasi (2021), the mother needs to provide lots of social and emotional support to children while the father provides more of physical support. Couples with satisfying marital relationship are more warm and supporting toward their children, and such children are more likely to succeed in academic work.

Theoretical Review

The Structural Theory of Marital Stability

The structural theory was propounded by Minuchin in 1974. The theory states that marital problems arises where the personality of one partner is swallowed up by the personality of the other partner and problems also come up where one partner's interest is in conflict with the general interest in the marriage. It is a theory that focuses on marital stability especially where one partner in the marriage has the irrational tendency to take charge over his or her wishes on the other partner. The structural theory of marital stability is a well known theory for family and marital counseling, as it proposes that marital stability should be promoted so that it does not affect the social, academic and moral development of children. According to the theorist, marital stability can only be achieved when one member's interest is in harmony with the general interests of the marriage, and children when children are taught moral values that promotes a peaceful and harmonious family life. The sense is that people who are in relationship or who wishes to be in relationship should ensure that the interest of one partner does not affect the other partner negatively which can bring about marital disharmony to the general interest of the relationship.

The theory of differential association is relevant to this work as it explains that divorce and separation which are components of broken home or marital instability can affect both the family members and as well as academic success of children. The theory has clarified the fact that children learn to adjust positively to academic work if the parents are supportive and establish a home environment were peace and harmony prevails. A child needs to be taught moral values from parents in order to develop good behaviour and live a responsible life. If parents fail to model good

behaviour and inculcate moral values into children's mind, the young ones may likely to exhibit deviant behaviour and fail to adjust positively to the demands of academic activities.

Literature Review

Divorce in Marriage and Academic Success of Students

Divorce is the process of dominating a marriage or marital union by an official and legal process. Divorce is the act by which a valid marriage is dissolved legally, usually freeing the parties to remarry (Eyo, 2018). A divorce happens when two people who are married dissolved their marital union through signing of legal papers that makes each of them single again. Divorce can be temporary or permanent. It is temporal when there is still hope of coming together after the relevant laws must have been put in place. This is to ensure that issues that created the temporal separation are settled. But if the divorce is permanent, it means there is no hope of coming together. In Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District, divorce or dissolution of marriage is a judicially administered process that legally terminates a marriage that is considered as no longer viable by one or both of the spouses and permits both of them to remarry. It entails canceling the legal duties and responsibilities of marriage and dissolving the bonds of matrimony between two persons. According to Potter (2017), the legal process involved issues of spousal support, child custody, child support, distribution of property and division of debt, these matters are usually only ancillary or consequential to the dissolution of marriage.

Divorce is an aspect of broken home because both parent do not live and enjoy marital relationship together. According to Igbinsosa (2014), life after divorce and separation can be very stressful for both the child and the parent. Children from such homes are often face financial strain and lack parental involvement and support of their education. Ayodele (2017) argued that environment were a child funds himself goes a long way in determining his or her learning ability and academic success.

Divorced homes may bring about stress, tension, lack of motivation and frustration which can impact negatively on students' academic success. Igbinsosa (2014) stated that children of divorced or separated families are not always motivated to undertake academic work with zeal and commitment. Children from divorced home do not only perform poorly in academic work but also tend to become disruptive in the classroom. Yakubu (2017) noted that students from divorced homes usually disturb others who are ready to learn in the classroom as result of poor parental control, supervision and deprivation of needs.

According to Ereke, Elendu, Nwafor and Agwu (2022), divorce may result in a child being entrusted to other people that are different from parent. The authors added that a child raised under surrogate parents often suffers dissemination and some psychological deprivation and such emotional frustration can be carried over to the school. Instead of listening to the teacher and taking down notes, such children usually have little or no interest in the learning materials. In most cases, children from divorced homes usually display truant behaviour and other illicit conducts which may hamper their academic success.

Divorce correlate positively with diminished academic success of students. Yakubu (2017) conducted a research on the influence of broken home on academic performance of students in Paikoro, Niger State, Nigeria. The author found that students from divorced families are most likely to perform poorly in academic work than those from intact families. Kinard and Renherz (2016) earlier found that school children who experience parental divorce are more prone to

perform worse academically than their peers from intact families in both test and examination scores.

Separation in Marriage and Students Academic Success

Marital separation is a condition alive spouses in a manage stop living together without setting divorced. A separation can be initiated informally or there can be a legal separation with a formal separation agreement filed with the court (Smith, 2014). Marital separation is a state where the partners choose to live apart with or without a court order. Berticat, Durand, Raymond and Faurie (2017) described a separated family as a family situation whereby a part or one of the parties has gone to court in order to have agreement drawn up regarding the financial support of wife and children or custody of children. The couple may come to live together again and in such situation, the separation is nullified. Where divorce is in view, the partners may end up not getting married to each other.

Separation occurs when husband and wife separate from each other through either natural causes (death) or by human cause (divorce, separate among other) leaving the care and responsibility of the children to one parent ((Crawford, 2014).). When a family separates, the child is deprived of parental affection, concern, feelings of security, social opportunities and physical necessities of life. Musa and Dosunmu (2022) noted that separation often live parents angry with each other; and that children from such homes suffers abilities to perform well in academic works and exhibit truant behaviour in school. The authors added that a child who experiences parental separation most times undergo a great deal of pains, confusion and anger which may cause the child to rebel. Eyo (2018) maintained that the academic success and behaviour of children living with a separated is highly limited due to poor parental care, support, supervision and academic encouragement. Children who live with a separated parent usually feel unsecured, experience emotional stress and develop low self-esteem towards academic achievement.

Berticat, Durand, Raymond and Faurie (2017) conducted a research on the link between parental separation and decreased performance in French high school students. In one of the findings, the authors revealed that parental separation decreases students' academic success in terms of their performances in school subjects. Adeboye, Odebode and Chukwuma (2021) added in their finding that students who live with separated parent do not attain high academic success like those from intact families.

Statement of the Problem

Academic success of students is measured, engagement in educational purposeful activities, acquisition of desired knowledge, skills and competences and academic achievement in school subjects. Students are expected to participate fully in academic work and develop must interest in it so as to achieve academic success. Sadly, in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District the researcher observed a decline in students' academic success. This is evidence in their lackadaisical attitude to studies, as some of them use to jump through the window on noticing that their social studies teacher is coming to teach them. Instead of the students to show deep interest in the subject by attending classes regularly, reading textbooks, doing and submitting assignment on time among others, some students display truant behaviour, refuse copying notes in the class and even lose concentration during classroom lessons. These and many other obnoxious attitudes of students towards academic work may be due to family challenges such as divorce and separation. Hence, the problem of this study is to find out whether divorce and separation could hamper students academic success in secondary schools. Therefore, this study aimed to determine the correlation

between divorce, separation and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for the study:

1. What is the relationship between divorce in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District?
2. What is the relationship between separation in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between divorce in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District
2. There is no significant relationship between separation in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District

Research Method

The correlational research design was used for the study. The population for the study comprised all the 15,222 senior secondary two (SS2) students in the 63 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Directorate of Planning and Research Statistics, Akwa Ibom State Secondary Education Board, Uyo, 2023). A sample size of 375 SS2 was selected for the study using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination table. This table indicates that if the population is between 15,000 and 20,000, a sample size of 375 will be representative of the population. A balloting method of random sampling was used to sample 25 public secondary schools out of 63. Thereafter, the same random sampling method was used to select 15 students from each of the sampled schools for instrument administration which gave a total of 375 sampled respondents. The researcher's designed instrument titled "Divorce, Separation and Academic Success of Students Questionnaire (DSASSQ) was used for data collection. The DSASSQ had two sections. Section A contained 16 items, 8 items each on divorce and separation while section B contained 10 items measuring students' academic success. DSASSQ were measured in a four point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. The instruments were given to two lecturers in Department of Educational Foundations, Akwa Ibom State College of Education, Afaha Nsit. to assess its face validity. To establish the reliability of the instrument, internal consistency reliability technique was used. Here, the instrument was administered on 30 SS2 students in a selected school not included in the sample of the study. Data collected were subjected to Cronbach Alpha statistics, which yielded the overall reliability index of 0.76 for the independent variables and 0.88 for items measuring students' academic success. This index according to Crawford (2014) is a very high reliability index since reliability coefficient is above .50. Therefore, the instrument was deemed reliable for use in the study. The questionnaire instruments were personally administered on the respondents in their respective schools by the researcher together with two informed research assistants. Data generated were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between divorce in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District?

Table 1: Correlation analysis of responses between divorce in marriage and academic success of secondary school students

Variables	n	$\sum x$	$\sum x^2$	$\sum xy$	r-value	Remark
		$\sum y$	$\sum y^2$			
Divorce in Marriage (x)	375	5416	76984			
Students Academic Success (y)	375	5494	74718	75527	-0.66	Low Negative Relationship

Researcher’s field work (2024)

Result in Table 1 shows a correlation value of -0.66. From the decision rule, it is noticed that a low negative relationship exists between divorce in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District. The implication of this result is that students are less likely to achieve academic success if they are raised by divorced parent.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between separation in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District?

Table 2: Correlation analysis of responses between separation in marriage and academic success of secondary school students

Variables	n	$\sum x$	$\sum x^2$	$\sum xy$	r-value	Remark
		$\sum y$	$\sum y^2$			
Separation in Marriage (x)	375	5426	76884			
Students Academic Success (y)	375	5494	74718	75355	-0.69	Low Negative Relationship

Researcher’s field work (2024)

Result in Table 2 shows a correlation value of -0.69. From the decision rule, it is noticed that a low negative relationship occurs between separation in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District. The implication of this result is that students living with separated parent are less prone to achieve academic success and vice versa.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between divorce in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.

Variables	n	$\sum x$	$\sum x^2$	$\sum xy$	r-value	r-crit	Decision
		$\sum y$	$\sum y^2$				
Divorce in Marriage (x)	375	5416	76984				
Students Academic Success (y)	375	5494	74718	75527	-0.66	0.196	Not Sig.
Researcher’s field work (2024)		Not Significant; P<.05; df = 373; critical r = 0.196					

Table 3 shows that the calculated r-value of -0.66 is less than the critical value of 0.196 at the degree of freedom of 373 and at .05 significant levels. Hence, the null hypothesis is therefore accepted. This implies that there is no significant relationship between divorce in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between separation in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.

Variables	n	$\sum x$	$\sum x^2$	$\sum xy$	r-value	r-crit	Decision
		$\sum y$	$\sum y^2$				
Separation in Marriage (x)	375	5426	76884				
Students Academic Success (y)	375	5494	74718	75355	-0.69	0.196	Not Sig.
Researcher’s field work (2024)		Not Significant; P<.05; df = 373; critical r = 0.196					

Table 4 shows that the calculated r-value of -0.69 is less than the critical value of 0.196 at the degree of freedom of 373 and at .05 significant levels. Hence, the null hypothesis is therefore accepted. This implies that there is no significant relationship between separation in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.

Discussion of Findings

The researcher made a combined discussion of findings from the research questions and hypotheses of the study.

Result from research question one and hypothesis one revealed a low negative and insignificant relationship between divorce in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District. This could be true because children of divorced or separated families are not always motivated to undertake academic work with zeal and commitment due to stress, tension, lack of motivation and frustration experienced as a result of divorce. This finding is in agreement with that of Kinard and Renherz (2016), which revealed that school children who experience parental divorce are more prone to perform worse academically than their peers from intact families in both test and examination scores. This finding is also in tandem with that of Yakubu (2017), who found that students from divorced families are most likely to perform poorly

in academic work than those from intact families. Therefore, it is observed from this finding that divorce in marriage may inhibit students' academic success.

Result from research question two and hypothesis two revealed a low negative and insignificant relationship between separation in marriage and academic success of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District. This could be true because children who live with a separated parent usually feel unsecured, experience emotional stress and develop low self-esteem towards academic achievement. This finding is in line with that of Berticat, Durand, Raymond and Faurie (2017), which revealed that parental separation decreases students' academic success in terms of their performances in school subjects. This finding also conforms to that of Adeboye, Odebode and Chukwuma (2021), that students who live with separated parent do not attain high academic success like those from intact families. Hence, it is obvious to note from this finding that broken home circumstance such as separation may impact negatively on students' academic success.

Conclusion

Based on finding of this study, it is therefore concluded that divorce and separation in marriage does not enhance students' academic success, since young one from such homes may encounter many challenges in their family and school life which can negatively affect their academic success.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were drawn from the findings:

1. Religious leaders and marriage counsellors should enlighten parents on the need to stay together as husband and wife, persevere and tolerate each other in marriage so that young one can develop positive attitude towards academic work.
2. Parents should put their children into consideration before they plan for divorce or separation as they are the ones to suffer the emotional, physical and social consequences.

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